

EFFECTIVE INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING FL TO MEDICAL STUDENTS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6535350>

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Annotation: *This article is devoted to improve teaching foreign language with the help of modern interactive methods and providing sources of learning English based on interactive methods and technologies. The article deals with the most prominent and crucial issues of using interactive games in the classroom and implementing it with the theoretical and practical approaches. The article discusses also possibilities of teaching medical terms in English by utilizing interactive techniques and developing professional skills of the medical students.*

Key words: *interactive methods, techniques, strategies, approaches, innovation, medicine, medical terms, role of teacher, learner-centred lesson.*

Аннотаци: *Статья посвящена совершенствованию обучения иностранному языку с помощью современных интерактивных методов и предоставлению источников изучения английского языка на основе интерактивных методов и технологий. В статье рассматриваются наиболее важные и важные вопросы использования интерактивных игр на уроках и их реализации с теоретическими и практическими подходами. В статье также обсуждаются возможности преподавания медицинских терминов на английском языке с использованием интерактивных технологий и развития профессиональных навыков студентов-медиков.*

Ключевые слова: *интерактивные методы, методики, стратегии, подходы, инновации, медицина, медицинские термины, роль учителя, личностно-ориентированный урок*

Regarding with a lot of developments, reformations and new inventions in all disciplines, requirement for learning foreign language is emerging with catching more and more attention of modern community. This factor is putting high responsibility and creativity for current and future teachers of our society. The major problem is how to conduct the lessons and gain efficiency of learning process in teaching foreign language for the learners who have different learning propositions in their skill.

Henceforth, it is really significant to select appropriate methods and techniques to complete expected resourceful outcomes. Meanwhile, innovative developments and discoveries have been explored in every field of education up to date thorough reformations and progressions connected with teaching foreign language, mainly English have contributed to boost the higher quality of teaching foreign languages both students of foreign languages and the students who have their own area. According to Javid (1), English language teaching "pedagogy has undergone tremendous changes over the last few decades, and individual learners and their differences have become major areas of interest." in ELT research". ESP is a learner-centered approach and specific learners, their linguistic and cognitive abilities. The nucleus is non-linguistic requirements. ESP courses (both academic and occupational) are designed for students who want to study English for work in a post-academic setting or for academic purposes in a pre-occupational setting. Yogman and Kaylani (1996) conducted a four-week English for business course and presented their findings to confirm that ESP learners need a certain degree of proficiency(2).The two-year study concluded that the experimental group that English for medical purposes (EMP) students were taught using locally designed teaching materials based on linguistic and non-linguistic needs. performed noticeably better not only in English but also in their content classes The findings strongly suggested that commercially available teaching materials are unable to. Many research studies in the Arab world and elsewhere have focused on learners' ages, attitudes, learning strategies, and motivation (3). Sifakis defines an ESP learner as "a person who is an expert in his own field and who can perform his various duties adequately in his mother tongue." Adults with a strong educational background but English weaknesses, according to him, are ESP learners. According to Dudley- Evans and St. John, ESP courses are typically designed for adults. Adults' learning behaviors can be better understood when compared to pre-adults or adolescents, who are dependents and are strictly supervised by their parents and teachers. They are at ease in the restricted and directed environment of formal schools and universities. They pursue their studies without having a clear goal in mind. Abbot (2012) referred to this phenomenon as "learning without any effective and distinct methods for teaching any foreign language". Adulthood learning characteristics received a lot of attention in "the learning and learner-centered" approaches of the previous years (Hutchinson and Waters, 1987). According to research, learning adulthood is not only associated

with the learner's age, but also with the learner's learning attitude and "the way a learner approaches a learning situation." An ESP learner has typically progressed beyond the "total reliance on teacher" stage and has attained the "level of maturity where he can not only evaluate information for himself but also make decisions about alternative options of learning procedures. According to Robinson, learning adulthood necessitates that ESP teaching can be extended beyond the classroom and into other modes, such as self-access. Study, project work, cooperative learning, and other forms of learning should be incorporated into the curriculum programme. According to research, ESP students should be actively engaged. To ensure full participation and encouragement of program participants, participants were involved in the collection of content materials, curriculum creation, and teaching methodology. Adams-Smith (2013) recommends that the content of ESP courses should be versatile to meet the needs of students any ideas. Sifakis has declared that the role of ESP teachers has become all-encompassing and challenging, based on the adult learning tendencies of ESP learners participants. Dudley-Evans have stated that "we regard ESP teaching as extremely important. "As a result, we use the term "practitioner" rather than "teacher" to emphasize that ESP work entails far more than just teaching" (4).

They have identified the five key roles for ESP practitioners who must carry out their work as a (n):

1. a teacher
2. course creator and material supplier;
3. collaborator
4. an investigator;
5. assessor;

An ESP practitioner's role as a teacher "more and more pronounced as the instruction becomes more specific". According to DudleyEvan, ESP teaching entails teaching skills related to "macro skills" of four language skills such as "importance of listening or reading for learning that is, the significance of writing for an audience." Additional research studies have also emphasized the "heavy demand" of not only having knowledge of scientific discourse language. It has been argued that ESP teachers are not "specialists in the field, but in teaching English," because their subject is English for the profession but not English for the profession (5). A professional ESP teacher should be able to transition students from one professional field to another without taking months. An experienced ESP practitioner only carries the required "tools, frameworks, and principles of course design" and

applies them to new content subjects. Course designing and providing relevant materials is one of the most important aspects of ESP teaching. The needs of ESP learners are specific and ready-made teaching materials do not suit their learning objectives. Another important aspect of the ESP teaching process is the selection of appropriate methodology or methodologies. Much research has provided profound insights into the fact that no single teaching methodology can suffice address the diverse and unique needs of ESP learners and practitioners. To run an effective ESP course, you must choose from a variety of teaching methodologies.

The specific demands of modern challenges in the field of ESP have compelled ESP practitioners to "move away from following one specific methodology" and choose "techniques and activities from a range of options of language teaching approaches and methodologies," and this trend is known as an eclectic approach. This method requires the teacher to "decide what methodology or approach to use based on the aims of the lesson and the learners in the group." Widdowson proposed that appropriate teaching methods be used positioned "at the very heart of the operation with course design aimed at servicing its needs requirements" and to address their specific requirements. Scientific analyses of specific learners' diverse linguistic and non-linguistic needs form the foundation of a successful ESP course because they specify "what" and the "how" of such courses Meeting these specific requirements necessitates a decision in terms of methods and approaches. According to Xiao-yun, eclecticism in language teaching holds that while no single language teaching method can meet all of the teaching needs, many methods can. Methods provide insights that should be used. It has become an additional burden for ESP practitioners to understand various teaching methodologies and approaches in order to select the most appropriate ones as well as components of these by employing a diverse approach. Hutchinson emphasized the importance of considering methodological aspects of ESP teaching in order to cater to the individual needs of ESP learners. Five principles have been identified to justify the problem-solving and task-oriented nature of communicative exercises: information transfer, information gap, jigsaw, task dependency, and content correction. As in this fast-moving world technology is playing crucial role in advancing every field of our civilization. Teaching English language is regarded to be initial stage to improve professional skills of students following the regulations of teaching ESP genres. As an example, we can take into consideration the importance of teaching English for future lawyers using various interactive

methods to increase communicative competence of students. From theoretical point of view it will be better to contemplate most useful and valuable strategies and techniques in using interactive methods to enhance communicative competence of ESP learners. As an ESP genre court procedure can be taught with fascinating interactive games and tactics taking into account challenges and achievements of the exploring issue. Noticeably, the students who learn English for specific purpose as well as the students whose profession is a lawyer have a high tendency to learn foreign language in order to develop professional skills and increase communicative competence. In order to upgrade communicative competence of future lawyers many types of interactive methods can be used during tutorial lessons. Dealing with most outstanding interactive methods and its techniques the following methods are regarded as an effective and practical during the most lessons which were taught and utilized by many teachers of ESP. Brainstorming, Stellar Explosion, Think-Pair-Share, Snowball, The Philips 6/6, Case Study and others can be comprehensive and reasonable ways of building up communicative competence of the students mostly by improving vocabulary acquisition for the given theme(6). According to S.T. Boghici he used brainstorming and stellar explosion for his students in teaching music encountering some challenges in using those methods in practice, however, later those methods began to be put into practice. Currently, documentaries of Law, issues are being performed in English language, that's why, English is considered to be a dominant factor to learn for future lawyers. Considering various difficulties while teaching Law in teaching grammar, vocabulary, phonetics and other competences we can improve communicative competence of the learners with the help of interactive methods. Hence, before improving communicative competence of the students it is incredibly imperative to practice with vocabulary skills. Teacher at the beginning of the lesson explain the theme introducing new vocabulary associated with the theme. After imagination and cognition will be formed in their mind about the topic then it will be easier for the students to discuss and share their opinions with each other during the lessons. While teacher explaining court procedure and ask students to find out and exchange their own solutions for the given issue brainstorming would be the most useful experiment to solve the given problem such as; what is wrong here with the legal decision proclaimed by the judge? Do you think that is the right of the human defended in this judicial inquiry?. The Philips 6/6 method consists in making up six groups, which are asked to produce new ideas in

six minutes starting from a given topic. It is comparable to brainstorming and the 6/3/5 method, its goal being to increase the creative spirit.

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